

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397

p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 5

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

MAY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue V (May 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

¹John Patrick S. Ondoy

²Arvin Orilla Palmones

BSEd III English Students
Mindoro State University - Main Campus
Oriental Mindoro, Philippines
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20092818

Frugality is the New Mentality

"You must gain control over your money or the lack of it will forever control you."
– Dave Ramsey.

If there is one thing that vexes us the most, surely, it would have to be numbers and Mathematics. Just a glance at the digits on the board makes our hearts race to death. Computing and solving is a bitter pill to swallow, an uphill battle we cannot conquer – except when it comes to money.

Two weeks ago, an episode in Kapuso Mo Jessica Soho (KMJS) exposed the skeleton in the closet of public-school teachers in the Philippines, a debt of abyss. As reported by Alliance of Concerned Teachers, 75% of 800, 000 public school teachers are in debt, leading to a staggering total amount of 319 billion pesos debt in 2-years. Worst case, one unearthed her life due to extreme depression, we cannot help but shake our heads in disbelief. Offering empathy is the least we could do, as for us, they are someone's wife, someone's mother, who wishes the best for their family. However, the damage has been done. But just like we always say, prevention is better than a cure.

Before it's too late, we must be cautious in managing our finances, or else, it will take charge of controlling the steering wheel of your life, and you can start as early as now. Even if you're still a student, you should not be careless with your allowance. Micro practices can have a macro effect, take frugality for instance, an action that guides us to spend our money wisely and effectively.

As college students who rent a boarding house, budgeting is not just a practice for us; it is the toolkit to survive the week and to make ends meet. Splitting our monthly allowance is like slicing an onion into pieces; you cannot help but cry. It was divided into rent, groceries, fare, internet fee, projects, and a lot more. Who would not be frugal in this situation? That's why we formulated best practices to keep our heads above water.

For the very first week of the month, we settle the bills as early as possible to avoid bills from piling up. After that, purchasing goods in the local market is recommended, as prices are incredibly low and still good for health. That follows the soul of budgeting, making

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 5

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue V (May 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

a meal plan that secures a menu for the whole week. Sometimes, we have to endure having three meals with the same viand, but trust us, that is for the best. This allows us to monitor what we have spent and prevent further spending, since it has already been fixed. For internet connection, what saves us from allocating a relatively large portion of money is splitting the cost of mobile data and using one phone as a mobile hotspot.

These simple habits work because they take the guesswork out of our spending. By knocking out our bills in the first week, buying our food at the local market, sticking to a strict meal plan, and sharing a hotspot, we make sure that we actually have enough to last until the end of the month without any stress.

We are happy to share our strategies for spending money wisely. No, we are not cheap; we are calculating the pluses, minuses, times, and divides of life. Adding a penny to savings, diminishing unnecessary expenses, multiplying resources, and apportioning allowance in light of frugality.

Financial literacy matters. It is now more than ever.